

REPRESENTATION OF UNTOUCHABILITY AND GENDER VIOLENCE IN THE NOVEL “UNTOUCHABLE” BY MULKRAJ ANAND

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Abstract

Bakha is a sweeper who strives to lead a better life. He has a sister named Sohini who is a tender and graceful girl. Pandith Kalinath asks her to sweep the courtyard of his house in the temple. Bakha travels to the city to clean the streets on behalf of his father, but touches a caste Hindu, leading to abuses, humiliation, and indignity. The novel suggests three solutions to untouchability: covert into Christianity, abolition of untouchability, and the introduction of a modern flush system. The novel takes place in Bulasha, a cantonment town in Punjab, and is based on the life of the untouchables and Bakha, the central figure in the novel. Anand's father was a Regimental Head Clerk in the Indian Army and his work reflects his knowledge of military life. The scenes and sights, customs and traditions, ideas and beliefs of Punjab form the background to the novel, and the exclamations, swear words, and abuses used in the novel are a rendering of military life and Punjabi life in general.

Key Words: *colony, untouchables, sexual abuse, Harijana, flush system, christianity.*

I. Introduction

Anand's *Untouchable* deals indirectly with an aspect of Gandhian struggle for freedom in the thirties. Anand tells the story of Bakha, an 18-year-old untouchable boy who is awakened by his father to clean public latrines. While walking along, he is touched by a man. But he is beaten down for defiling the man which is really the man's own fault. At the moment to the surprise of this boy a Muslim comes to his rescue. Then cursing his lot he reaches the temple where to his dismay he sees the Brahmin priest trying to molest his sister Sohini, a sweeper in that temple. He foils the attempt but the frustrated priest escapes into the crowd shouting that he has been polluted. After performing his duties he approaches to certain houses for food. But he realises that there is no food for the scavengers like him when

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there is enough for the holy man walking with the readymade blessings of God. Really for the essential services rendered by him he gets nothing but the sheer callousness of the beneficiaries.

II. Main Discussion

Bakha, an 18-year-old, is tasked with cleaning three rows of public latrines in Bulshah village. Bakha's father Lakha, sister Sohini; younger son Rakha is sweepers and cleaners of Public latrines. The researcher identifies that these all characters are from outcaste people. They are called as untouchables. The novel writes at the time of 1935, before Indian Independence movement. It is evident that the existence of hierarchies of society. The four hierarchies exist during this time. The Brahmins, the Vaishyas, the Kshatriyas, and the Sudras all these hierarchies constructs on the basis of caste and traditional works.

The main characters of the novel, Bakha, Lakha, Rakha, Sohini, are outcastes from the Hindu society. They are part of the Untouchable community, who have the same value system and identity as the Hindus. They include scavengers, leather workers, barbers, water-carriers, grass-cutters, and other outcaste people. It is evident that the Hindu community people have higher status compare to the outcast people. In this novel, the two communities are represented. One is Hindu community who are superior in the society. And the others are outcaste and untouchable communities. They are inferior in the society.

The Bakha lives in a mud wall hut. During night time, it is very cold, he doesn't have good blankets to sleep. Until morning wind blows continuously, it penetrates through the skin. The place where Bakha and his family live is very stingy. It is not a good place for living human beings. The study highlights that the writer wants to give good respect and nobility for Bakha. It is because of his work that cleans and sweeps three rows of public latrines. But, it is condemns for him because of his filthy profession. He identifies as sub-human, outcaste people from the society.

The upper caste people consider they are pure and superior community. Lower and outcaste people are not allowed to fetch water from public wells. If they take, well will be contaminates. And are they not allow to access from nearby stream. The upper caste people have the same value system that they are superior. They feel and follow the traditional caste feelings.

It is common for the upper caste community people to use abusive language towards the outcaste people. Gulabo, a high caste woman, scolds Sohini for being an illegal begotten and an eater of dung and drinker of urine. The study highlights that communities are formed by shared value systems and beliefs. Here, all upper caste people are sharing the different values and belief systems. That's why, they are constitutes different upper caste community. At the same time, other outcaste people are sharing the different value and belief system. Therefore, these characters constitute the untouchable community.

After cleaning of public latrines, Bakha walks in the morning towards other public area, he touches a Brahmin man in the public. He slaps on the face of Bakha and shouts that they are low caste vermin and must take a bath to purify themselves. Caste is a major parameter for identifying the communities. It is evident in the above paragraph. Why the Brahmin feels that I am defiled by the physical touch of Bakha. He believes that I am Brahmin belongs to the upper caste. He belongs to untouchable caste. The study highlights that the Muslims and British people are no problem for the upper caste people of the Hindu society. They can easily touch them. Only Hindus and outcasts who are not sweepers are allowed to sweep. The sweepers are only looks the high caste people as untouchables.

Another incident from the novel is also clearly evident in the present caste system in Indian society. Pandit Kalinath asks Sohini to come in afternoon to clean the Temple. In temple, Pandith Kalinath molest her, she shouts loudly for the protection but Kalinath turns that matter into other way by focusing on the arrival of Bakha into the temple. He makes the temple defile. Pandith Kalinath has to wash again the temple for purify. It takes lot of sacrifices.

The study highlights that the Gandhi speech forms a new dimension in the novel. Whole people of Bulshah village are eagerly waiting for the arrival of Mahatma Gandhi. He makes a speech on the national day at Nellore. He wants to remove the practice of untouchability. He says that in my next life I want to be born as an outcaste, as an untouchable. This is a main dream of the Mahatma Gandhi. At the same time, Gandhi denotes the national and freedom moment in India. The whole people of India crave for the freedom from the British government. The writer of this fiction is imaging the idea of 'nation'. Modern novelists imagines nation as a community. Therefore, all people of the village are participating in the Gandhi speech function. The study focuses on nation and nationalism is also a imagined community of the modern novelists.

III. Conclusion

The researcher observes that the novelists use novel form to criticize the social evil practices and social problems in the society. The novelists advocate for equality of rights, privileges and opportunities for all. The research observes that the abolition of cleaning public latrines, untouchability is the main arguments of this novel. The writer gives three conclusions for the abolition of untouchability. They are: first one is the introduction of modern flush system. Flush system is a toilet that disposes of human waste by using the force of water. Secondly, to convert outcaste and untouchables into Christianity where there is no such untouchable practices. And last the abolition of untouchability.

The study observes that this novel represents the two major community experiences. They are: First one is upper caste community. It means, all the people of upper caste community share same value and belief system which is carries by the traditional caste system. Major characters in the novel like Pandith Kalinath, Ram Charan Singh, Colonel Hutchison, Marry Hutchison, Gulabo, Charat Singh, Ramanand, Hakim Bhagawan Das are represent upper caste people. Throughout the novel, all these characters feel same value and belief system that they belong to upper caste. They have different identities in which they can't entertain the outcaste people into their home.

The second community is untouchable community. It constitutes the people from the outcaste and untouchable colony. Bakha, Lakha, Rakha, Sohini are representing this community. All these untouchables feel same value system and belief that we are inferior to Hindu caste people. All these characters suffers, cries lot from the upper caste Hindu people. The writer imagines how a nation should be? If India will become a nation, it must not have all these social problems.

The Hindu society consists with traditional heirarchised structure of caste. Traditionally, there are four classes of people in India: Brahmins, Vaishyas, Kshatriyas, and Sudras. The Sudras are considers as outcaste people from the Hindu society. This is because they are doing filthy and scavenger works. The novelist represents outcaste people community experience realistically. All upper caste people are feeling superior and sacred to them. If the upper caste people touched by a outcaste man, they will become defiled. These attitudes clearly witnesses the practice of caste system according to the traditional hierarchies is evident.

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